

Cranky Uncle

Developed by: John Cook, Monash University & Goodbeast

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Keywords

Climate-change Education, Cognitive Bias, Conspiracy Theories, Critical Digital Skills, Critical Thinking, Information, Inoculation Theory, Media Literacy, Misinformation, Rhetoric

Introduction

Cranky Uncle is an educational digital game developed in 2020 by John Cook, a scientist at Monash University, in collaboration with the creative agency Goodbeast. The game aims to train students in how to deal with misinformation by becoming a 'Cranky Uncle' themselves, a science denier and conspiracy theorist who uses various argumentation techniques to reject the general scientific consensus. Through humorous cartoons with a thematic focus on climate change, deep insights into the tactics of science denial are provided to help resist future attempts at misleading persuasion and improve critical thinking. As they play, players are put to the test through various quiz types, identify deceptive arguments, receive instant feedback on correct or incorrect quiz answers, and move up and down a scoring system.

Facts

Release date:	2020
Developer:	John Cook, Monash University & Goodbeast
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	Single player, can also be played in groups
Format:	Hybrid
Time frame:	Completing all the denial techniques takes about 30 minutes, depending on how many quiz questions the players answer.
Languages:	The game is available in 13 languages
Environment:	Access to smartphones or computers
Material:	Guidelines for Teachers
Price:	Available free of charge

Resonance & Criticism

Since *Cranky Uncle* mainly addresses climate change and the associated discourse on its consequences and risks, the game's core topic is challenging to beat on timeliness grounds (Cook et al., 2023). Especially during the recent COVID-19 pandemic, the ubiquitous spread of disinformation returned to the forefront (Cook, 2021), and the educational game attracted

significant attention. In 2023, the game's inventor received the Publication Award for Excellence in Information Literacy, presented by Purdue University, for an article on the game's relevance and effectiveness (Cook et al., 2023).

Game Principle & Process

Figure 1. Screenshots from *Cranky Uncle* (John Cook, Monash University & Goodbeast). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

At the beginning of the game, the players examine various explanations of the denial techniques to identify them later. Furthermore, at the end of each unit, quiz questions are asked to test and deepen the players' knowledge. These quiz questions can always be selected and played through in the main menu, regardless of the score. After completing the explanation phase and the quiz, players receive “cranky points” that represent their progress in the game. Additionally, teachers can use this point system to grade their students, with a set number of “cranky points” corresponding to a particular grade or reflecting the student's level of engagement.

According to the developer John Cook, *Cranky Uncle* is based on the psychological research field known as “inoculation theory” (Cook, 2021), a form of inoculation that, rather than fighting a virus, aims to immunize against misinformation by acquiring new knowledge. This vaccination can take place in two ways, as Cook (2021) explains, through fact-based and logic-

based approaches. During the game, players are confronted with the 'FLICC' system (Cook, 2021), the five main techniques of science denial. With the help of a wide range of examples from these areas of fake experts, logical fallacies, impossible expectations, cherry-picking, and conspiracy theories, players can gain a thorough overview of the most dangerous strategies of science denial.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

The game aims to build resistance to problematic theories and statements, and to identify fallacies and conspiracies directly. Regarding the focus on climate change, these skills are future- and science-affirming lessons that can be particularly valuable for young learners. The detailed insights into the tactics of science denial and its rhetorical devices also offer students the opportunity for in-depth education. However, the effectiveness of the game heavily depends on the preparation and follow-up of the game content by the teachers. Before playing, there should be an introduction to the general topic, and after the game, students could reproduce what they have learned through role-playing games or similar activities (Cook & Autonomy Co-op, 2021).

To make it easier to use the game in the classroom and to prepare for and follow up on it, guidelines for teachers have been published that suggest a range of activities to supplement and reinforce the game (Cook & Autonomy Co-op, 2021). These guidelines minimize teachers' workload, as they only need to register for group codes on the game's website. Since it can be assumed that all players have smartphones or computers, little or no external equipment is needed. As a result, teachers in over 17 countries have adopted Cranky Uncle into the curricula of primary, secondary, and higher education classes, and it has already been used across a variety of subjects, including biology, environmental science, English, and philosophy.

Effectiveness

The humorous presentation of serious topics aims to explain complex subjects simply and maintain engagement and interest among players (Cook, 2021). A study by Cook et al. (2023) demonstrated that Cranky Uncle's humor-based pedagogical approaches can transform complex topics, such as climate change and its consequences, into engaging and entertaining teaching units. In addition, the game promotes players' critical thinking abilities, which are particularly important in today's world for helping them see through false reasoning and avoid being tempted by disinformation (Cook et al., 2023).

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Given that Cranky Uncle addresses certain ideologies and thus also political affiliations, some players may reject or question the game's topics. Trust and understanding must be established in the group in advance so that no one feels excluded or attacked. It is equally important that teachers feel confident in their knowledge of the game's subject matter to work effectively

with the game. The teacher's guide provides resources that convey sufficient background knowledge to get a good overview of the topic and the game's approaches (Cook & Autonomy Co-op, 2021).

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

Sources

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